

MOSLANGAN MANBALI NOCHIZIQLI SHREDINGER TENGLAMASI

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Annotatsiya. Mazkur ishda moslangan manbali nochiziqli Shredinger tenglamasi bilan bog'liq tengliklarni keltirish o'rganib chiqilgan.. Hozirgi davrda nochiziqli tenglamalar uchun bunday tengliklarni keltirib chiqarishning bir nechta usullari mavjud.

A operator ushbu

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} i|u|^2 + 2i\xi^2 & -iu_x^* - 2\xi u^* \\ iu_x - 2\xi u & -i|u|^2 - 2i\xi^2 \end{pmatrix}$$

ko'rinishda bo'lsin. Yetarlicha silliq va $(L(t) - \xi I)v = 0$ tenglamaning yechimlari bo'ladigan funksiyalar sinfida

$$[L, A] = LA - AL = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -2|u|^2 u^* + u_{xx}^* \\ -2|u|^2 u + u_{xx} & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

funksional tenglik bajariladi.

Ushbu

$$(L(t) - \xi I)f = 0, \quad \frac{\partial \phi_n}{\partial x} = \Psi_n^T f, \quad n = 1, 2, \dots, 2N \quad (2)$$

chiziqli tenglamalar sistemasini $f, \phi_1, \phi_2, \dots, \phi_{2N}$ o'zgaruvchilarga nisbatan qaraymiz. Bunda $\Psi_1, \Psi_2, \dots, \Psi_{2N}$ funksiyalarni hozircha aniqlanmagan ikki komponentali vektor-ustun. Bu yerda f ikkinchi tartibli kvadrat matritsa, $\phi_1, \phi_2, \dots, \phi_{2N}$ ikki komponentali vektor-satrlar.

$f, \phi_1, \dots, \phi_{2N}$ lar orqali $g_0, g_1, \dots, g_{2N}$ kattaliklarni quyidagicha ifodalaymiz

$$g_0 = \frac{\partial f}{\partial t} - Af + \sum_{n=1}^{2N} \Phi_n \phi_n, \quad (3)$$

$$g_n = \Psi_n^T \sigma_3 f + i(\xi - \xi_n) \phi_n, \quad (4)$$

bu yerda $\Phi_1, \Phi_2, \dots, \Phi_{2N}$ hozircha aniqlanmagan ikki komponentali vektor ustunlar. Demak, g_0 kattalik ikkinchi tartibli kvadrat matritsa $g_1, g_2, \dots, g_{2N}$ kattaliklar esa ikki komponentali vektor-satrlar.

Endi $\Phi_1, \Phi_2, \dots, \Phi_{2N}, \Psi_1, \Psi_2, \dots, \Psi_{2N}$ matritsalar qanday shartlarni qanoatlantirganda (2)-(4) tengliklar bilan aniqlanuvchi $g_0, g_1, \dots, g_{2N}$ kattaliklar

$$(L(t) - \xi I)g_0 = i \sum_{n=1}^{2N} \Phi_n g_n, \quad \frac{\partial g_n}{\partial x} \equiv 0, \quad n = 1, 2, \dots, 2N. \quad (5)$$

tengliklarni qanoatlantiradi aniqlashtiramiz.

Unchalik qiyin bo‘lmagan hisoblashlar orqali (5) tengliklar o‘rinli bo‘lishi uchun

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial t} + [L, A] = i \sum_{n=1}^{2N} [\sigma_3, \Phi_n \Psi_n^T], \quad (6)$$

$$(L - \xi_n I) \Phi_n = 0, \quad n = 1, 2, \dots, 2N,$$

$$(\tilde{L} - \xi_n I) \Psi_n = 0, \quad n = 1, 2, \dots, 2N$$

tengliklarning o‘rinli bo‘lishi zurrur va yetarli bo‘lishini ko‘rsatish mumkin. Bu yerda

$$L(t) = i \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} & -u^*(x, t) \\ u(x, t) & -\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{va} \quad \tilde{L}(t) = i \begin{pmatrix} -\frac{\partial}{\partial x} & u(x, t) \\ -u^*(x, t) & \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \end{pmatrix}.$$

$n = 1, 2, \dots, N$ da

$$\Phi_n = \begin{pmatrix} \varphi_{1,n} \\ \varphi_{2,n} \end{pmatrix}, \quad \Psi_n = \begin{pmatrix} \psi_{1,n} \\ \psi_{2,n} \end{pmatrix}$$

deb belgilasak, $\xi_{N+n} = \bar{\xi}_n$ uchun

$$\Phi_{N+n} = \begin{pmatrix} \varphi_{2,n}^* \\ \varphi_{1,n}^* \end{pmatrix}, \quad \Psi_{N+n} = \begin{pmatrix} \psi_{2,n}^* \\ \psi_{1,n}^* \end{pmatrix} \quad (7)$$

tengliklar o‘rinli. Demak,

$$i \sum_{n=1}^{2N} [\sigma_3, \Phi_n \Psi_n^T] = 2i \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \gamma^* \\ -\gamma & 0 \end{pmatrix},$$

bunda $\gamma = \sum_{n=1}^N (\varphi_{1,n}^* \psi_{2,n}^* + \varphi_{2,n} \psi_{1,n})$.

$L(t)$ operatorning ifodasi va (1), (6) tengliklardan

$$iu_t - 2u|u|^2 + u_{xx} = -2i \sum_{n=1}^N (\varphi_{1,n}^* \psi_{2,n}^* + \varphi_{2,n} \psi_{1,n})$$

kelib chiqadi. Bu tenglamaga moslangan manbali nochizikli Shredinger tenglamasi deyiladi.

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